

THE HARMONY OF TURKISH PEOPLE’S VIEWS ON EDUCATION IN YUSUF KHOS HAJIB’S WORK “KUTADGU BILIG”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11282190>

Annotation. *It is expressed views on education in Yusuf Khos Hajib’s work “Kutadgu bilig”, which is the harmonious heritage of Turkish people.*

Key words: *harmony, behavior, quatrain, education.*

A nation rich in cultural and educational heritage is a nation in the glory of history. The future of such a nation will be bright. Thankfully, the Uzbek people have such a great history and are able to preserve thousands of antiques in their history. Such a huge cultural and educational heritage of the nation has been and will remain an extremely important and invaluable resource in raising children in the spirit of love and loyalty to the whole human society.

Undoubtedly, there are many works in our literature, especially in our classical literature. Among them is Yusuf Khos Hajib’s work “Kutadgu bilig”. The work is unique in terms of its high artistry, advanced universal and national ideas and values. Although it was created in the 11th century, its educational and literary value has not completely decreased, on the contrary, as a result of the writer’s poetic interpretations, completely new interpretations of many moral and spiritual phenomena have reached us. Poetry has appeared, it lives as a connoisseur of goodness, an opponent of evil, a thirst for justice, and an avenger of oppression. In this sense, Yusuf Khos Hajib, who laid the foundation stone of our ancient Turkish literature, contains many thoughts related to the spirituality of all Turkish people in the rich verses of the epic “Kutadgu bilig” and evil are separated by two poles.

It is known that the uniqueness of a poet or writer’s creativity, his ability to use words and the extent to which he used artistic image tools can be illuminated by analysing them.

Literary scientist Baqijon Tokhiev, who founded the scientific study of Yusuf Khos Hajib’s work, says the following about the means of artistic representation used in the work “Kutadgu bilig”: its content is determined by how much it is aimed at revealing its inner world. In fact, we can see that even a writer like Yusuf Khos Hajib did not use artistic art tazad as a tool in his work. Let’s focus on the following poem:

Biligsizga davlat yarashsa kelib,
Biliglikka artuq yarashur tegib.
Biligsiz bila tursa davlat qali,
Biliglik bila turg’a teng tush ko’rib¹.

Content: If the state that comes to the ignorant is suitable for him,
A state that has come to a wise person is extremely suitable for him.
If the state decides to be ignorant,
He decides that it is suitable and appropriate for the wise.

Through this quartet, the writer talks about the relationship between educated and uneducated people in the possession of the state. The state is with the ignorant, but the wise knows

¹ Абдурахмонова Б.М. Таълим босқичларида “Кутадгу билиг” асарини ўрганишнинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари. Пед.ф.н.-дисс.-2007.-160.

that the state in the hands of the wise will lead him to perfection. The poet condemns ignorance and glorifies wisdom, that is, knowledge. He tries to justify his opinion by contradicting the words of the ignorant and the wise.

A person can learn from the good throughout his life, but what about the bad? It is up to the individual to distinguish why he should learn from the bad. Solving the problem is in the judgment of the person, in fact the law of life is this: one can expect good from the wise and bad from the ignorant.

Kishi aslingga, ko'r, qilinchi tanuq,
Qilinchi ne ersa ko'r, asli ul-o'q.
Kimning asli ezgu, qilinchi o'ngay,
Esiz aslingga kendu qilqi tanuq².

Content: A person's true nature is determined by his actions. The way they act is the way they are. Whoever has a pure and good origin, his behavior and deeds will be good. The root of evil is its verb. As the writer creates a contrast by contrasting good and bad words in these verses, no matter how much a person tries to be mysterious, he cannot cover his inner world even with a veil. His actions, behaviour and speech give information about this person, reveal his identity. The poet considers that a person who does not care about others, who cannot share in the sorrows of others, is evil. Whoever has a bad name in the light world, it is better not to live. Only a person who lives virtuously can enjoy life, life is worthy of him. In the third and fourth stanzas of the quatrain, Yusuf Khos Hajib creates a contrast by quoting good and bad words and encourages people to always do good.

Yusuf Khos Hajib teaches people about several ways of leaving a good name in the world. It reminds us that after coming into the world, we should do good deeds:

Esizka – so'kush, ezgu- o'g'du bilar,
O'zungga baqa ko'r, qayusun qilur,
O'zung ezgu bo'lsa, ating o'g'dilig',
Qali bo'lsa esiz, so'kush, ey silig.

Content: The bad will be scolded (reprimanded), the good will be praised. Which one do you choose? If you are good, you are worthy of praise, if you are bad, you are condemned to be insulted, O good-natured. And in the manner of teaching people, he gives an example that Zahhok left a bad name in the world because of his bad behavior, and Faridun's happiness was caused by his good behavior:

Sukushlug nelug buldi Zahhokdak utun,
Nelug o'gdi buldi Faridun qutun.

A person's character and behavior is a mirror that shows his identity. Therefore, the poet, who believes that a person should refrain from evil and strive to have good qualities, uses the words good and evil appropriately. Yusuf Khos Hajib strongly condemns those who harm people. The poet's thoughts on this matter are as follows:

Yusuf Khos Hajib created beautiful examples of artistic art *tazad* by referring to the traditional images of folklore and our classical literature - good and bad, wise and ignorant, friend and enemy, religion and ignorance.

Yusuf Khos Hajib contrasts friend and enemy by using the proverb "If you have thousands of friends, it seems few, but if your enemies are only one it seems many":

²To'xliyev B. Yusuf Xos Hojib. "Qutadg'u bilig" (Saodatga eltuvchu bilim). -T.: -Cho'lpon nashriyot matbaa uyi. - 2007.

Dushman birgina bo'lsa ham zarari ming-mingdir,
Minglab do'sting bo'lsa ham ozligi birga tengdir.
Kishi dushmanidan foyda qilmagin,
Agar qilgan bo'lsa, o'zining ko'rguligidur.

The poet is a supporter of people living in harmony and friendship regardless of their race and nationality.

In the work of the poet, the dignity of a person rises to the highest. They say that whether a person is young or old, his value is determined by his knowledge, intelligence and intelligence. In order to show that he will gain or be devalued, he interprets the person who speaks the truth - wise, and the one who does not speak the truth - by quoting ignorant sentences:

Bilib so'zlasa so'z bilingka sanur
Biligsiz so'zi o'z bashini eyur.
O'gush so'zda artiq asig' ko'rmadim,
Yana so'zlamishda asig' bulmadim.

The poet says that a real person should speak correctly and be correct:

Kishi chinda so'z desa zebo durur,
Necha muxtasar bo'lsa avlo durur.

Yusuf Khos Hajib's lyrical hero is a smart and wise person. Age is not important for intelligence and wisdom. Because in order to be intelligent and wise, it is necessary to be knowledgeable and truthful. In the philosophical generalizations of both creators, the belief in the power of the human mind is clearly expressed by its knowledge, intelligence and intelligence. Yusuf Khos Hajib's thoughts on education are a common example for the spirituality and enlightenment of the Turkish people.